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A Review on Composite Railway Sleepers: Global View, Life-Cycle Sustainability, and Regional Gaps in West Africa

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ABSTRACT

Composite railway sleepers encompass a diverse range of material systems, including polymer-based composites manufactured from virgin and recycled polymers, as well as hybrid formulations tailored for structural and environmental performance. They withstand deterioration, insect infestations, and humidity, resulting in enhanced durability and prolonged lifespan. Longer replacement intervals, lower maintenance requirements, and reduced life-cycle costs are all outcomes of these attributes. In addition to offering excellent strength and damping, composites allow for circular end-of-life reuse. According to life-cycle assessments, plastic sleepers can reduce emissions compared to wood, and as recycling and carbon prices increase, they can become more affordable. This review synthesizes recent (2018–2025, with projections to 2026) global advances in composite sleeper technology. We compile innovations in materials (fiber-reinforced plastics, rubber blends, and biodegradable formulations). We integrate findings on track performance, durability testing, and emerging standards, illustrating how composite sleepers are entering service in sustainable rail programs. Recent developments include bamboo-based composites for enhanced bending resistance and recycled formulations from Biatic Group (2023), with global market growth projected at an 8%-9% compound annual growth rate (CAGR) to USD 2.5 billion by 2033. Despite these developments, a significant gap persists in West Africa: regional policy frameworks do not address the deployment of composite sleepers, and no published studies assess them in tropical environments. As evidenced by Ghana's first concrete sleeper plant inauguration (in 2017) and JICA safety studies, infrastructure deficits persist amid timber dominance. The social and economic advantages of rail are noted by African governments, but so is the fact that there is a significant financial and infrastructure deficit on the continent. There is an urgent need for research and policy in West Africa, as seen by the lack of standards or pilot programs for composite sleepers. This review lays the groundwork for future studies and policy creation in tropical and Sub-Saharan railway contexts by highlighting sustainable, scalable track solutions. Engineers and legislators look for long-lasting, environmentally sustainable sleeper solutions to update African rail networks and promote economic growth.

1 | Introduction

Railway sleepers, also known as crossties in some regions [1], are fundamental components of the track structure, responsible for

maintaining gauge, transferring wheel loads, and ensuring overall stability [2]. For clarity: Composite sleepers refer to those made from fiber-reinforced polymers (FRPs), hybrids, or other nontraditional materials; plastic sleepers specifically denote

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those from recycled or virgin polymers; polymer sleepers encompass both but emphasize polymeric matrices, distinguishing them from geopolymer or concrete-based variants [2]. For over a century, timber has been the dominant material due to its adaptability and ease of handling. However, timber's limited durability, vulnerability to biological degradation, and limited supply of quality wood have accelerated the shift toward alternatives such as concrete and steel. While concrete offers strength and durability, it is heavy (high embodied carbon, though superior in longevity and stability under high-speed traffic [3]); steel, though durable, is vulnerable to corrosion and exhibits challenging ballast interaction [4]. These persistent shortcomings have prompted the global railway industry to explore more sustainable and durable solutions. Composite materials have emerged as promising alternatives, offering durability, reduced maintenance needs, and extended service life. Composite railway sleepers encompass a broad class of engineered materials that combine two or more constituents to achieve enhanced mechanical or durability performance. It is crucial to distinguish between different categories of composite sleepers. While the term "composite" can broadly refer to any multimaterial system, this review focuses primarily on polymer-based composites. These are further categorized into recycled plastic sleepers, FRP sleepers, and hybrid sleepers, which combine a polymer shell with a concrete or timber core. Polymer-based composite sleepers form a distinct subgroup in which a polymer matrix—typically thermoplastic or thermoset—is reinforced with fibers or fillers such as glass fibers, carbon fibers, or recycled plastic aggregates. FRPs [6], recycled plastics [5], and hybrid polymer-concrete [6] systems have all been proposed as next-generation railway technologies. Their advantages include resistance to degradation and weathering, enhanced fatigue performance, and opportunities for integrating recyclability. Past research has laid the groundwork for this discussion. Notably, the early works of Ferdous et al. [7] and Ferdous and Manalo [8] and Ferdous et al. [9] provide one of the most comprehensive analyses of composite railway sleepers, documenting the failures of traditional materials, the promise of polymer composites, and the challenges hindering widespread adoption. For instance, the work of Ferdous et al. [10] remains a cornerstone in the field, particularly for its detailed evaluation of structural behavior and early field trials in the Australian context. However, the composite sleeper landscape has evolved considerably since then. From 2018 to 2025, research has expanded beyond structural mechanics to include sustainability metrics, life-cycle assessment, recyclability, and the integration of smart technologies [11]. Recent advancements feature FRPs combined with shape memory alloy (FRP/SMA) reinforcements for durability (up to 134% bending resistance). Ultra-high-performance concrete (UHPC) with fibers for 98% load increases, and market-driven innovations such as Biatec's recycled sleepers, with projections to 2026, show an 8% + compound annual growth rate (CAGR) globally. In West Africa, case studies such as Ghana's sleeper casting improvements highlight regional potential amid infrastructure gaps [12].

This gap underscores the need for an updated review that not only synthesizes the latest advances in composite sleeper technologies but also reframes the discussion around sustainability, scalability, and adoption worldwide, especially in West Africa. Unlike earlier reviews, this paper highlights developments

between 2018 and 2025, focusing on three areas: recent advances in material innovation, including natural fibers, nanocomposites, and hybrid systems; sustainability considerations, such as life-cycle environmental impact; and industrial adoption, with emphasis on policy, standardization, and deployment of these technologies in other parts of the world (West Africa subregion). The aim of this review is to provide a comprehensive and forward-looking synthesis of composite railway sleeper technologies that extends beyond earlier reviews. By bridging material science, sustainability analysis, and infrastructure practice, the paper seeks to offer researchers, engineers, and policymakers actionable insights to accelerate the transition toward resilient and sustainable railway systems, including under transient loadings such as vibrations and impacts.

2 | Evolution of Railway Sleeper Materials

The development of alternative sleeper technologies has been motivated by the well-documented failure modes of traditional sleepers (timber, concrete, and steel): fungal decay and end-splitting in timber, rail-seat abrasion and cracking in concrete, and corrosion and fatigue in steel. Previous reviews by Ferdous et al. [9] and Manalo et al. [4] provide a detailed review of these failure mechanisms and early composite sleeper developments. This paper does not repeat that technical synthesis; instead, we briefly summarize the main drivers (durability, maintenance cost, and material scarcity) before concentrating on developments and sustainability analyses published after 2017. Recent evolutions include hybrid reinforcements (e.g., FRP/SMA for reduced prestress losses [13]) and sustainable composites in emerging markets such as Ghana's railway projects. As illustrated in Figure 1, traditional timber sleepers often succumb to failure modes such as cracking, abrasion, and decay, particularly in humid environments, driving the evolution toward more resilient and sustainable composite materials in modern railway technology.

2.1 | Existing Materials Used for Railway Sleepers

2.1.1 | Timber

Traditional timber railway sleepers are used on railway tracks all throughout the world, but problems with deterioration, scarcity of supply, and environmental concerns are making it difficult for them to be used widely [14]. In West Africa, these issues are worsened by tropical climates accelerating decay, with infrastructure gaps leaving timber-dominant networks vulnerable. Africa's rail network spans only 66,000 km (vs. China's 160,000 km), facing annual funding shortfalls of \$68–108 billion [2]. Even though timber sleepers provide benefits including temperature resistance and effective vibration damping, they also need to be protected from elements such as sunlight, temperature extremes, fungi, and mold to avoid decomposing (e.g., in humid environments such as Ghana, where evaluations show 20-year degradation [15]). Timber sleepers have been shown to be practical and dependable in the railway environment over the years [16]. A defining characteristic of timber sleepers is their adaptability, as they can be modified to suit virtually any railway track geometry. Timber sleepers are a viable option because they are efficient to install and repair and also do not require expensive assembling equipment [17]. Although wood is highly workable and adaptable, its use causes deforestation, and as

(a)

(b)

FIGURE 1 | (a)-(b) Failure modes of railway sleepers (e.g., cracking, abrasion, and decay [8]).

a result, the environmental impact is particularly severe [18]. The most common sleeper material is hardwood timber. Currently, more than 2.5 billion timber sleepers are installed in railway tracks worldwide [4]. However, while the maintenance is lower compared to other materials, timber remains a widely adopted choice due to its established installation procedures [19]. Their vulnerability to mechanical and biological deterioration, which leads to failure, is their primary drawback [20]. The pressing requirement for substitute materials that strike a balance between sustainability and dependability in the railway infrastructure is highlighted by this environmental challenge and its vulnerability to deterioration. The utilization of chemical preservatives in timber sleepers not only poses environmental hazards but also introduces health risks. The most severe difficulty that the railway industry currently faces is a decline in the supply of high-quality wood for railway sleepers [4]. According to Manalo et al. [4], due to environmental concerns, efforts have been made to limit the use of creosote-impregnated timber sleepers and tighten production-process restrictions. “Creosote-impregnated” refers to wood that has been treated with creosote, a type of wood preservative. Creosote is a mixture of chemicals that is used to protect wood from decay and insect damage [21]. Reuse of sleepers exists, such as in home garden applications, but these are only for untreated timber sleepers [8]. However, the reuse of sleepers primarily extends to untreated variants, limiting options for recycling chemically impregnated timber products due to concerns over worker safety and associated environmental implications. Industries are also reluctant to recycle chemically impregnated timber products because of concerns about worker safety and environmental problems [11]. In an effort to replace timber sleepers with materials that will last longer and require less maintenance, the railway sector is looking into alternatives, including prestressed concrete and glass FRP (GFRP) composites [22]. Recent developments include engineered interspersed concrete sleepers designed to replicate the stiffness properties of timber sleepers, ensuring consistent track performance and load distribution between different sleeper types [21]. As depicted in Figure 2, timber sleepers in active railway lines, such as those enduring harsh tropical conditions in West Africa, visually demonstrate the ongoing challenges of biological degradation and structural vulnerability that necessitate the shift toward more sustainable alternatives.

FIGURE 2 | Timber railway sleepers in West Africa [23].

2.1.2 | Concrete

Concrete sleepers remain the most widely used sleepers globally due to their high stiffness, durability, and proven long-term performance under heavy axle loads [8]. However, their production is associated with high embodied energy, significant carbon emissions, and increased transportation impacts due to weight [24]. While composite sleepers offer reduced mass and better vibration damping, they often lack the established stiffness of concrete [9]. A balanced assessment of sleeper materials therefore requires consideration of both structural performance and environmental trade-offs [11]. Concrete sleepers gained widespread adoption in the 1950s. Its durability, dependability, stability, and ease of maintenance led to it becoming a crucial and increasingly common component of railroad tracks. [25, 26]. Concrete sleeper handling and installation are made easier by specialized lifting equipment, which increases productivity and decreases the need for physical labor. To maximize performance and longevity, concrete sleepers have experienced constant innovation [27]. Consequently, recent innovations have moved toward hybrid and nonprestressed variants to bridge this gap. Hybrid FRP concrete sleepers, which utilize pultruded profiles filled with concrete, have emerged to provide high load capacity with up to a 43% reduction in weight compared to monoblock sleepers [28]. Furthermore, research has shifted toward nonprestressed-reinforced concrete sleepers to address the resonance and low damping (~1%–3%) inherent in conventional prestressed designs [29]. Research on the advantages of using nonprestressed-reinforced concrete sleepers in railway infrastructure has emerged as a critical area of inquiry due to the

increasing demand for durable, cost-effective, and environmentally sustainable railway components. They are important because they can offer higher damping, less corrosion risk, and potentially lower maintenance and environmental costs compared to conventional prestressed concrete sleepers [30]. Recent work revisits nonprestressed sleepers using corrosion-resistant reinforcement such as carbon FRP (CFRP) laminates or CFRP/polyurethane layers, avoiding steel prestressing altogether [31]. Specialized track-relaying trains and mechanized hoisting systems have been developed to increase sleeper installation speed, track construction efficiency, and cost-effectiveness [32]. Prestressed concrete now makes up around 500 million of the railway sleepers in the world's railway networks, and each year their demand accounts for more than half of the total demand [8]. Prestressed sleepers, however, can suffer from resonance and low damping, increasing vibration problems and damage under high-frequency loads [33]. A breakthrough development is the laminated carbon fiber-reinforced polyurethane (L-CFRPU) sleeper, which avoids steel prestressing entirely. These sleepers exhibit damping ratios exceeding 50% and superior resonance resistance, maintaining structural integrity even after high-frequency impact loading. Such advanced designs mitigate the risk of sudden brittle failure associated with corroded high-tension tendons in prestressed systems [34]. Composite or fiber-reinforced nonprestressed sleepers can lower environmental impact, especially when using recycled polymers or rubber, and reduce harmful effects on the environment [35]. In the research of Ferdous et al. [7], concrete was not utilized in sleeper construction owing to its inherent tension weakness. Longer lifecycles and lower maintenance costs lead to economic and technological advantages. Conversely, prestressed concrete sleepers have the potential to mitigate environmental impacts compared to traditional materials [36]. The use of industrial waste materials such as fly ash and ground granulated blast furnace slag in the manufacturing process of prestressed concrete sleepers can contribute to carbon footprint mitigation and address waste disposal concerns [37]. In addition, the use of ternary blended concrete with partial replacement of natural coarse aggregate has been found to improve the strength characteristics of prestressed concrete sleepers [38]. Furthermore, the production methods of pretensioned long-mold flow and instant-demolded short-mold flow have been identified as having a higher automation level and lower efficiency, which can help reduce resource consumption and environmental impacts [39]. However, prestressed sleepers can suffer from resonance and low damping, increasing vibration problems and damage under high-frequency loads [31].

In regional contexts such as Ghana, the Atlantic Concrete sleeper plant (commissioned in 2017) continues to save the nation approximately USD 27M annually by localized production. However, as of late 2025, a significant infrastructure gap remains; the African Union's target of 30,200 km of new lines by 2040 highlights the urgent need for these high-performance, sustainable sleeper variants to close West African infrastructure deficits [12]. Despite these advancements, the substantial weight of standard concrete sleepers still poses risks of musculoskeletal and crushing injuries during installation [4, 40]. Therefore, a balanced assessment must weigh the structural benefits of new CFRP-laminated and hybrid materials against the logistical and environmental trade-offs of traditional concrete [41, 42]. Figures 3 and 4 illustrate concrete sleepers, including advanced

FIGURE 3 | Hybrid FRP-concrete tubular column [28, 43].

FIGURE 4 | Concrete sleeper [44].

hybrid FRP-concrete variants, demonstrating enhanced structural integrity and loading distribution in real-world applications.

2.1.3 | Steel Sleepers

Steel sleepers are important components that efficiently support and secure railroad tracks in railway systems [45]. They are available in a variety of shapes and forms, including steel-concrete composites [46], rail sleepers with trapezoid-shaped grooves [47], and steel sleepers for tramcar railways. Steel sleepers have been used in railways for several decades [19] and offer unique structural advantages, though their adoption remains limited in many regions due to specific drawbacks. Steel sleepers exhibit several positive attributes that make them suitable for certain applications. They provide excellent positional stability thanks to their shape and embedding in the ballast bed, which enhances track integrity [48]. Unlike wood, steel sleepers are not prone to decay and are not preyed on by rodents [14], making them resistant to biological degradation. They offer a more reliable and straightforward connection between the rail and sleeper, and studies have shown that steel sleepers can be intermixed with existing track, but only in a certain arrangement to minimize track geometry variance and sleeper service failure. In terms of vibrational behavior, steel sleepers can restrict vibration along the rail when equipped with stiff pads, contributing to reduced noise and smoother operations in comparison to some traditional materials [49]. Their ballast interaction is generally effective due to the inverted trough profile, which allows for strong interlocking with ballast particles when properly embedded, promoting stability under load [49]. In addition, steel sleepers demonstrate high lateral resistance, often generated through internal ballast interaction via their concave structure, making them suitable for tracks requiring enhanced resistance to

lateral forces [50, 51]. Overall, steel sleepers are resistant to adverse weather conditions due to high-strength, weather-resistant steels and creative sleeper designs, and they have a long lifespan of 30–40 years with low maintenance needs [4].

However, steel sleepers also have notable negative attributes that can limit their use. They require special attention during installation and tamping because of their inverted trough profile, which makes it difficult to load properly with ballast [52]. Observations of rail deflections under applied vehicle track loading have revealed that the settlement of steel sleepers is larger than that of adjacent timber sleepers, indicating that steel and adjacent timber sleepers do not carry an equal share of the imposed wheel weight [53]. Special steel profiles, notably the Y-shaped steel sleeper, can achieve very high lateral stiffness: Y-sleepers form a rigid frame that gives “very high horizontal positional stability” despite their low weight. In terms of vibrational behavior, steel sleepers may exhibit higher vibration transmission in mixed systems or under high-frequency loads compared to concrete alternatives, potentially leading to increased track wear [54, 55]. Ballast interaction can be problematic if embedding is insufficient, impairing overall track stability and leading to uneven load distribution [53]. While they provide high lateral resistance in optimal conditions, this can be compromised in poorly maintained ballast beds, resulting in reduced performance [61]. The use of steel–concrete composite structures in sleepers reduces corrosion and satisfies technical specifications for mechanized railway line maintenance [47]. As described in Li et al. [56], the design of strong railway sleepers with buffering elements and prestressed sections improves protection against large impact damage from passing trains. Moreover, steel sleepers are often considered uneconomical in certain regions and are utilized in fewer numbers due to high energy consumption during manufacturing and susceptibility to corrosion in humid environments [51, 54]. Their high electrical conductivity also makes them unsuitable for track circuiting [57]. Steel sleepers, as depicted in Figure 5, highlight the practical application of steel’s superior load-bearing capacity and minimal maintenance needs, particularly in regions prone to heavy freight.

2.1.4 | Plastic Sleepers

Sleepers are manufactured primarily from recycled or virgin high-density polyethylene (HDPE) or other polymers, often without significant fiber reinforcement [59]. The introduction of plastic sleepers in the railway industry is a combination of the search for alternative materials to wood and, more recently, the search for durable and more sustainable materials [40]. Plastic sleepers, as a subset of polymer-based composite sleepers, primarily use recycled or virgin polymeric matrices (e.g., polyethylene) without extensive fiber reinforcement, distinguishing them from FRPs or hybrids [60]. Plastic sleepers possess some interesting properties, such as high damping and a long lifespan owing to their good chemical and biological resistance, and offer the following performance advantages [61]: they are less susceptible to weather or decay, have constant elasticity, are stable, have a long service life, require less maintenance and repair, and are economical.

Reducing plastic and rubber waste through the use of waste materials to make plastic sleepers can also benefit the environment [62]. Compared to hardwood sleepers, plastic sleepers

can provide better moisture-proof and anti-corrosion performance [63]. The report of Kumar Bagal et al. [18] has called on upstream corporations to take responsibility for their role in plastic pollution by adopting a clear plan to transition production toward safe, environmentally sound, and sustainable materials. This is because plastic production is expected to triple by 2060, and lifecycle emissions from plastics are estimated to more than double, accounting for 4.5% of global emissions. Major industrial producers, such as IntegriCo Composites Inc., manufacture various types of composites for the industrial, defense, and aerospace sectors. Advanced composite materials development and manufacturing, such as glass fiber, carbon fiber, and aramid FRPs, are the areas of expertise for IntegriCo Composites Inc. Investigations have been conducted on recycled waste plastic sleepers as a viable substitute for railway use. The use of mixed plastic waste (MPW) composites in the creation of environmentally friendly railway sleepers has been the subject of numerous studies [64]. These composites have been created and evaluated for mechanical and environmental performance. They are primarily composed of MPW and glass fibers [65]. In a different investigation, sleepers with appropriate mechanical qualities were created by combining waste plastic with regenerated waste polypropylene (PP) and polyethylene, as well as fillers and additives [66]. Furthermore, it has been discovered that composites made of municipal plastic waste and reinforced with coal ash, with up to 60% coal ash added, are appropriate for railway sleeper applications [11]. According to life-cycle calculations by Thompson et al. [11], recycled plastic short-fiber plastic composites can outperform concrete sleepers in terms of cost and environmental benefits [67]. In addition, research on the dynamic characteristics of recycled composite sleepers has shed light on their viscoelastic behavior. Compared to traditional materials, sleepers made of recycled plastic offer various environmental advantages. Life-cycle studies show that recycled plastic short-fiber composite sleepers are more environmentally friendly than long-fiber composite sleepers, concrete, and wood [11]. One benefit of short-fiber plastic composites is that they are completely recyclable, which reduces waste and pollution. Their cost approaches that of concrete sleepers, even when only 50% of the sleepers are recycled [4]. Using recycled plastic sleepers also helps reduce the amount of plastic waste in landfills. The production of recycled plastic sleepers decreases the demand for stone mining and enables proper waste disposal. The building sector may contribute to a more sustainable and circular economy by reducing construction costs and the demand for traditional resources by using waste plastic. All things considered, using recycled plastic sleepers encourages resource efficiency and reduces environmental pollution. Turner and Filella [68] pointed out that railway sleepers made from recycled plastic sleepers may present health risks. According to the study, new PVC flooring made from recycled PVC contains dangerous compounds, including lead and bis(2-ethylhexyl) phthalate (DEHP), which can postpone the phase-out of these substances. Along with other potentially dangerous chemicals, orthophthalates such as diisononyl and diisodecyl phthalates (DiNP and DiDP) were also found in a sizable number of samples [69]. Grohs et al. [53] said these substances are hazardous to human and ecological health and may have unfavorable biological impacts. Thus, in order to guarantee the sustainability and safety of using recycled plastic sleepers in railway applications, it is imperative to expedite the phase-out of dangerous compounds and

(a)

(b)

FIGURE 5 | (a)-(b) Steel railway sleeper installation (a) (e.g., construction of a Y-shaped steel sleeper track (b)) [58].

improve transparency in the chemical compositions of plastics [70]. When compared to other sleeper kinds, short-fiber plastic composites, which are recyclable, offer possible cost savings and environmental benefits [11]. To completely comprehend the long-term health repercussions of utilizing plastic sleepers, more research would be required. Plastic sleepers are better alternatives when they produce functional requirements equivalent to those of concrete and wood sleepers.

A summary of the comparison of existing materials used in railway sleepers, as well as the environmental impact, is considered when selecting a sleeping material and is presented in Tables 1 and 2, adapted from Manalo et al. [4].

The table above details the primary environmental implications linked with each type of sleeper material in terms of manufacturing and maintenance.

3 | Composite Sleeper Technologies: Developments Since 2018

Recent years have seen a surge in composite sleeper innovations as sustainable alternatives to timber and concrete. Seminal research by Ferdous et al. [10] demonstrated that epoxy-bonded fiber composite sleepers can meet or exceed the strength of hardwood while using only 50% of the material. His prototype sleepers showed higher bending and shear capacity and were installed on a Queensland trial line, confirming practical viability. Building on this foundation, post-2018 research has focused on recycled polymer composites and novel low-carbon materials [5]. For example, a study by Yu et al. [72] reviewed recycled plastic sleepers and reported that short-fiber plastic composites (typically HDPE blended with rubber, glass fiber, or mineral fillers) can achieve high strength-to-weight ratios and excellent durability. These sleepers are lighter than concrete, resist weathering and decay better than wood, and allow full recyclability at the end of life. They also exhibit improved vibration damping compared to timber or concrete. According to Zhang et al. [61], the study of composite materials with 62.5% glass fiber and 20% PP greatly improves mechanical properties. When compared to composites without glass fiber, these materials achieve improvements in flexural strength, flexural modulus, tensile strength, compressive strength, and hardness of 315%, 623%, 296%, and 40%, respectively. In line with research on short-fiber plastic composites in railway sleeper applications, this

shows how recycled HDPE combined with glass fiber can achieve excellent strength and endurance [73].

Also, Ferdous et al. [9] note ongoing challenges: recycled plastic sleepers often have lower stiffness and reduced screw-holding capacity and can suffer creep deformation or voids if manufacturing is not tightly controlled. Contemporary improvements, such as adding synthetic fibers or optimizing polymer-filler mixes, are addressing these issues, and economies of scale are driving costs down to approach those of concrete sleepers [74].

In parallel, life-cycle studies have underscored the environmental benefits of shifting to advanced rail materials. Bilgili et al. [75] compared highway vs. railway systems via life-cycle analysis (LCA) and found that 100% rail transport dramatically cuts emissions relative to road. Notably, in their Turkish case study, the railway construction phase (assuming standard concrete sleepers) had far lower impacts than highway construction [76]. Still, they found that concrete sleepers alone accounted for roughly one-third of the construction phase CO₂ in a 1 km track. This suggests that replacing heavy concrete sleepers with lighter composites could further reduce the track's carbon footprint. A very recent LCSA of the Kayseri light-rail system by Gulcimen et al. [77] similarly showed that infrastructure materials (concrete and steel) and electricity use dominate life-cycle burdens. According to Orczyk's study in [78], energy use accounted for more than 90% of life-cycle costs, with an estimated 0.024 kgCO₂e per passenger-kilometer. These results confirm that electrically powered rail is naturally low carbon and that rail infrastructure may be made even greener by choosing low-impact materials (such as recycled composites).

Beyond recycled plastics, other composite designs have advanced since 2018. Polyurethane foam composite sleepers [79] (e.g., Sekisui fiber-reinforced foamed urethane [FFU] synthetic wood [80]) continue to be used in tunnels and specialized trackwork due to their light weight and water resistance. These sleepers match timber's bending stiffness while avoiding chemical preservatives, though high cost limits their use [41]. Geopolymer and hybrid sleepers [81] made from industrial waste (fly ash, slag, and rubber) are also emerging: these reduce cement use and exploit recycled content [29, 82]. Preliminary reports suggest geopolymer sleepers achieve comparable strength and stiffness to concrete, while further cutting CO₂ emissions. Such eco-sleepers

TABLE 1 | Comparative analysis of sleeper material properties [4].

Properties	Hardwood	Softwood	Concrete	Steel	Composite/plastic
Adaptability	Easy	Difficult	Difficult	Difficult	Easy
Workability	Easy	Easy	Difficult	Difficult	Easy
Handling and installation	Easy	Easy	Difficult	Difficult	Moderate
Durability	Low	Low	High	Low	High
Replacement	Easy	Easy	Difficult	Difficult	Easy
Availability	Low	High	High	High	Moderate (growing in Ghana)
Cost	High	Low	Very high	Very high	High initial, low lifecycle (saving 20%-50% over time)
Fasteners	Good	Poor	Very good	Poor	Good
Impact	High	High	Low	Medium	Medium-high
Weight (kg)	60-70	60-70	200-300	70-80	50-100
Tie ballast interaction	Very good	Good	Very good	Poor	Good
Service life, years	20-30	20	40-60	50	40-60+
Electric conductivity	Low	Low	Low (insulated standards)	Very high	Low
Maintenance	High	High	Low	High	Low

are not yet mainstream, but they illustrate the trend toward low-carbon materials in track design [83].

Key developments since 2018 thus include the maturation of recycled plastic and fiber-reinforced sleepers, new LCA-based comparisons that quantify their sustainability benefits, and continued optimization of composite designs [77]. Modern composite sleepers have reduced lifespan impacts and increased strength and durability. Modern polymer composites, for instance, offer great mechanical strength, good elasticity and durability, and improved damping properties in comparison to wood [14, 84]. When combined, these developments expand upon Ferdous et al. [10]’s initial research and suggest a future in which optimized composites and recycled materials will be essential components of sustainable track infrastructure. To illustrate the evolving landscape of composite sleeper technologies, Table 3 offers a comparative overview of key options, summarizing their material compositions, advantages, limitations, projected service life, and sustainability considerations, which underscore the shift toward more durable and eco-friendly alternatives to traditional materials.

3.1 | Challenges That Confront the Use of Composite Sleepers

According to Kumar Bagal [18], composite sleeper technology has emerged as a viable option for railroad track maintenance and sustainability. Due to problems with strength, stiffness, and dynamic qualities compared to conventional concrete, steel, or timber sleepers, the railway industry has not widely accepted composite sleepers for use in rail tracks, which is one of the hurdles facing the technology [98]. Furthermore, a major barrier to the broad use of composite sleepers made of recycled materials is the mismatch in features between them and conventional sleepers [99]. Moreover, a particulate-filled resin system is suggested as a viable solution to the insufficient screw-holding ability of polyurethane foam-filled composite sleepers [18]. However, there are still obstacles that must be solved before they can be widely accepted and used. This section discusses the most typical issues that arise while employing a composite sleeper.

3.1.1 | Strength and Stiffness Properties

Since composite sleepers are designed to replace traditional sleepers, their strength and stiffness should be comparable. One method for increasing the strength and rigidity of composite sleepers is to reinforce them with long fiber or steel bars. The high shear strength makes multidirectional fiber sleepers suitable for bridge construction. According to the findings of Manalo et al. [4], the ability of a sleeper to withstand shear force is especially critical for bridge applications (transoms), where the sleepers are subjected to considerable shear stress due to the location of rails and support beams, which are typically offset by roughly 250 mm in Australia. In order to increase the feasibility of composite sleepers for a variety of railway applications, particularly in crucial domains such as bridge building, creative solutions to the problems associated with guaranteeing maximum strength, stiffness, and shear resistance are required. Achieving better structural qualities for composite sleepers strengthens their potential as a reliable and sustainable choice in the context of railway infrastructure, as well as increases their application. Table 4 provides a comparative analysis of

TABLE 2 | Environmental effects of materials used for railway sleepers.

Material	Environmental effect
Timber	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A large number of trees are chopped down for the production of timber sleepers
Steel	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Resource-intensive production (e.g., iron ore mining); recyclable but high emissions if not green-sourced
Concrete	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • High embodied carbon and energy use; contribute to mining impacts, but recyclable aggregates mitigate this
Plastic/composite	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reduces landfill waste via recycling and lower lifecycle emissions (20%–50% vs. concrete) but leads to potential chemical leaching if not managed [71]

mechanical properties for common railway sleeper materials, emphasizing the trade-offs in density, flexural strength, modulus of elasticity, damping ratio, and service life that guide material selection for enhanced structural performance and longevity in modern rail infrastructure.

3.1.2 | High Cost

The declining quality and scarcity of hardwood timber, along with the increasing costs and environmental concerns associated with timber sleepers, have encouraged the exploration of composite sleepers; however, the high initial procurement cost of composites remains a significant market barrier [104]. The issues are further compounded by the limited adoption and implementation of composite sleeper technologies in rail lines [9]. Although recycled material is less expensive, it frequently lacks the strength, rigidity, and dynamic qualities of regular sleepers [18]. Innovation is needed to overcome these obstacles. For example, polyurethane foam can be used as an infill material, and particulate-filled resin systems can be used to increase strength and screw-holding capacity [105].

In comparison to other types of sleepers, composite sleepers such as GFRP composites and composite material sleepers offer cost-effectiveness [106]. It has been discovered that GFRP sleepers have mechanical qualities that are similar to those of timber sleepers, with the added benefit of being less prone to failure and damage [14]. Good vibration and noise reduction effects are achieved by the composite material composite sleeper, which is composed of an elastic composite material shell and a concrete core. It also decreases wave abrasion. Costs are further reduced by the sleeper's changeable shell [107].

Another proposed composite sleeper made of recycled HDPE and other materials showed sufficient strength to hold mechanical connections, with performance similar to timber sleepers and better than commercially available composite sleepers [108]. A composite structure sleeper with a polyurethane composite film coating improved impact resistance, strength, and weather resistance, prolonging the service life of the sleeper. A mutually embedded phenolic resin composite sleeper increased lateral strength by more than 50% and improved mechanical strength and lifespan [109].

The high prices of most composite sleeper technologies have been cited as one of the primary reasons for their limited commercial adoption. The cost of high fiber-content composite sleeper developments for both unidirectional and multidirectional fiber sleepers is around 5 to 10 times that of timber

sleepers. Nonetheless, a reduced life-cycle cost is anticipated to offset its high beginning cost, which, in order to attract the attention of the rail industry, should be comparable to, or somewhat greater than, that of conventional ones.

3.1.3 | Dynamic and Transient Loading Effects on Composite Sleepers

One key advantage of composite sleepers over traditional materials (e.g., timber, concrete, or steel) is their enhanced vibrational damping properties, which mitigate the effects of dynamic loading. For instance, polycarbonate and polyethylene plastic sleepers reinforced with fiberglass demonstrate damping of impact loads and sound absorption comparable to timber sleepers. These sleepers provide superior acoustic dampening compared to metal or concrete alternatives, reducing noise and vibration transmission along the track [4]. Composite sleepers exhibit unique behaviors under transient loading, vibrations, and impact loadings due to their viscoelastic properties and material composition [110]. These characteristics allow them to effectively manage dynamic forces encountered in railway applications, enhancing their performance compared to traditional materials. Transient loads refer to short-duration events such as wheel impacts or sudden braking, while dynamic loads encompass ongoing vibrations from train passage, track irregularities, or environmental factors. Typical railway axle loads range from 20 to 30 tonnes (196–294 kN), with wheel loads (half-axle) commonly around 100–150 kN statically, but dynamic amplification can increase these by factors of 1.5–2 or more due to speed, irregularities, and voids under sleepers. Mechanical testing reveals a compressive strength of 43.9 MPa and a flexural strength of 40–60 MPa, enabling them to handle transient impacts without immediate failure, though challenges such as creep under sustained dynamic stresses can lead to permanent deformation over time [7, 93]. Under repeated train load cycles, sleeper materials can develop damage or permanent set. The fatigue behavior of composites depends on the matrix and fiber. Fiber-reinforced sleepers (GFRP/CFRP) typically have significantly high fatigue life under tensile/bending loading [111], but cracks can initiate at stress concentrations or joint interfaces [112]. One study on GFRP laminates showed that at high stress levels, fibers fail in tension, while at lower stresses, failure is governed by stress concentrations; nonetheless, well-designed FRP sleepers can endure millions of cycles without fiber fracture. In practice, bond quality (e.g., between sandwich layers) and matrix microcracking are critical for fatigue life [113]. Conversely, polymer-matrix sleepers (recycled plastics) exhibit viscoelastic creep under sustained loads. Laboratory tests indicate that polymer sleepers

TABLE 3 | Comparative performance of new composite sleeper technologies.

Technology	Material composition	Key advantages	Limitations	Service life (years)	Sustainability notes	Reference
Recycled plastic sleepers	HDPE, PET, rubber, and additives	Low cost, moisture/decay resistant, diverts plastic waste	Lower stiffness than timber/concrete, fastening issues	30–40	Diverts waste, recyclable if thermoplastic-based	[5, 85, 86]
FRP sleepers	Glass/carbon fiber + epoxy/polyester resin	High strength-to-weight ratio, corrosion-resistant	High cost, limited recyclability	40–50	Durable but thermostat disposal is problematic	[10, 72, 87]
Hybrid FRP-concrete/PU	FRP skins + concrete/PU core	High stiffness, good load distribution, reduced material use	Complex manufacturing, higher initial cost	50+	Potential reduced material footprint; limited recycling pathways	[88–91]
Natural fiber composites	Hemp, bamboo, jute, bioresins	Low-cost, renewable, biodegradable, lightweight	Durability concerns, moisture absorption	15–25 (projected)	Renewable, but long-term performance uncertain	[92–94]
Smart composite sleepers	FRP with embedded sensors	Real-time monitoring, predictive maintenance	Prototype stage, cost-intensive	TBD	Enhances sustainability through optimized maintenance	[95, 96]
FFU (fiber-reinforced foam urethane)	Long glass fiber + PU resin	Lightweight, proven for > 40 years in Japan, recyclable waste PU	High production cost	40+	Proven recyclability at pilot scale	[10, 90, 97]

TABLE 4 | Typical mechanical properties of railway sleeper materials.

Property	Hardwood timber	Prestressed concrete	Polymer composite (FRP)	Recycled plastic (unreinforced)
Density (kg/m ³)	800–1100	2400–2600	1600–1900	900–950
Flexural strength (MPa)	50–80 (high-grade structural hardwoods)	40–70 (effective structural bending capacity due to prestress; base material tensile strength is approximately 5 MPa)	100–400	15–40
Modulus of elasticity (GPa)	10–15	30–40	4–25	1.0–2.5
Damping ratio (%)	~2.0–4.0	~0.5–1.0	~2.0–5.0	~5.0–8.0
Service life (years)	15–25	40–50	50+	30–50

Note: The flexural strength values reported here refer to effective structural bending capacity for prestressed concrete sleepers (accounting for prestressing effects), rather than the base material tensile strength of plain concrete. This ensures a fair comparison with the load-bearing performance of other sleeper types under railway loading conditions. These values are representative of current literature by Salih et al. [93], [100], [101], [102] and Lofy et al. [103]. This indicates why FRP is superior to unreinforced plastic.

can heat up and soften under continuous high-frequency cycling, leading to stiffness loss. Indeed, continuous fatigue tests cause creeping and thermal buildup in polymer sleepers, which may not reflect real track loading [114].

Long-term field evidence is still scarce, but available data suggest creep and permanent deformation are concerns for plastic composites. For example, recycled-polyethylene sleepers have shown measurable permanent set after 1 million cycles, and plastic composites tend to lose 10% stiffness under cyclic load, whereas timber loses 8%–12% [115]. Critical research gaps exist in standardized impact testing protocols, transient loading characterization, frequency-dependent property mapping across temperature ranges, and long-term field performance validation beyond 30 years [116].

Urethane foam and fiberglass composites, such as the FFU sleepers developed by Sekisui Chemical Co. Ltd., show similar dynamic behavior to timber, with an impact bending strength of 41 MPa and a modulus of elasticity of 8100 MPa [41]. Acoustic and dynamic analyses indicate effective vibration isolation, making them suitable for high-vibration environments such as turnouts, tunnels, and bridges [117]. Installed in over 925 km of track across Japan, Germany, Austria, and Australia, these sleepers maintain performance under repeated dynamic cycles, with a design life exceeding 50 years [8, 118]. For transient loads, their rail-seat compression of 58 MPa withstands peak impacts from heavy axles [93]. As illustrated in Figures 6 and 7, composite sleepers demonstrate superior vibration attenuation and flexural strength under dynamic and transient loads. For example, Figure 6 depicts the normalized amplitude decay of sleepers under a simulated impulse load. The concrete (red) shows a prolonged decay period due to its low damping ratio ($\zeta \approx 0.01$), whereas the composite sleeper (blue) exhibits rapid energy dissipation ($\zeta \approx 0.05$). This higher attenuation reduces the transmission of high-frequency vibrations to the ballast and surrounding environment. The bar chart in Figure 7 highlights the superior effective flexural strength of FRP composites (FRPCs) and the high bending capacity of prestressed concrete sleepers compared to traditional materials.

3.1.4 | Moisture

Moisture has a variety of effects on composite sleepers' durability and function. Moisture sensitivity in fiber-enforced polymer sleepers is governed primarily by the resin matrix rather than the fiber type. Most commercial FRP sleepers employ glass fiber reinforcement due to cost and durability considerations, whereas carbon fibers are rarely used because of their high cost. While indirect methods such as diffusion, capillary activities, wicking actions, and osmosis are possible, direct moisture intrusion can happen through preexisting channels created by faults in the composite system. Moisture can deteriorate the thermo-mechanical characteristics of composite panels, including the honeycomb structure's cells and the face-to-core bond line [119]. The pace at which moisture penetration rises can lead to microcracking in composite materials as a result of moisture absorption [4]. Depending on the matrix and interface materials utilized, different types of moisture, such as water buildup, might affect the mechanical properties of the composites in different ways. When building composite sleepers that can survive weather conditions and keep their performance and durability, it

FIGURE 6 | Comparison of vibration attenuation and damping response between prestressed concrete and polymer composite sleepers. Adapted from data presented by Ferdous et al. [10], Zeng et al. [57], and Aktas et al. [33].

is essential to comprehend these particular types of moisture and their impacts.

The mechanical performance and durability of polymeric composite structures can be impacted by moisture exposure [120]. FRPCs that absorb moisture may experience weight growth, plasticization, hygrothermal swelling, and debonding between the fiber and matrix [97]. Moisture exerts a profound influence on the long-term performance of FRP-wood composites [121], and this deterioration is often caused by internal defects such as void and microfractures [122]. Although carbon fiber composites are susceptible to moisture absorption, newly created fluorinated epoxies exhibit less moisture absorption and may have superior long-term durability [123].

The performance and longevity of composite sleepers can be impacted by moisture in a number of ways. Water aging is one particular kind of moisture that can cause environmental deterioration of the sleepers' mechanical qualities [124]. Bound

FIGURE 7 | Comparative effective flexural (bending) strength of railway sleeper materials. Values reflect structural performance under rail-seat loading, not base material tensile strength. Adapted from the properties report in Silva et al. [40].

water is another kind that exists in the cell walls of sleepers and can be found in multiple local environments. Furthermore, moisture may result in secondary crystallization events in the sleepers, which may mitigate the combined impacts of ultraviolet (UV) light and hygrothermal stress. Moreover, moisture can permanently harm the fibers in hemp fiber-reinforced sleepers, lowering their modulus and tensile strength [125]. Ultimately, maintaining the long-term performance and longevity of composite sleepers requires an understanding of and ability to manage these various sources of moisture [99].

Railway components are frequently subjected to moisture [122] from rain, frost, snow, hail, and dew, which greatly contributes to the deterioration of a polymer composite since moisture may degrade not only the polymer resin but also the reinforcing fibers. This absorption might react with the polymer matrix or impose internal stress, reducing the overall mechanical characteristics of the composite. According to Brito et al. [126], the adverse effects of moisture deterioration, sometimes referred to as hydrolytic degradation, on the performance and durability of polymer composites make it a major problem. In this process, moisture is absorbed by the composite material, which causes the polymer

matrix to disintegrate and the composite's characteristics to deteriorate. Moisture degradation in polymer composites can significantly affect their mechanical properties, thermal stability, and overall performance. Recent findings highlight several critical factors regarding environmental degradation:

- Environmental degradation in polymer composites can occur due to moisture absorption, temperature fluctuations, and chemicals present in seawater.
- The degree of water absorption and its probable location can be linked to the resultant degradation in mechanical properties.
- Understanding degradation is necessary for developing lifetime assessments of polymer composites.

In addition, polymer composites' mechanical qualities, thermal stability, and overall performance can all be negatively impacted by moisture degradation, which is a serious problem. Comprehending the degradation mechanisms and devising tactics to alleviate their impact, including employing protective coatings or refining the composite design to reduce moisture absorption, are crucial. Pandey et al. [123] noted that through a number of methods, including diffusion, capillary action, and microcracks, moisture can permeate the composite. Intruded water molecules can induce various degradative mechanisms once they permeate the composite matrix. They have the potential to cause debonding and delamination by upsetting the polymer-matrix contact. The polymer chains can also be hydrolyzed by water, which results in chain scission and a drop in molecular weight. The type of polymer, the microstructure of the composite, the surrounding environment, and the existence of protective coatings or treatments are some of the variables that affect how much moisture deterioration occurs. Certain polymers, such as nylon and polyesters, are more prone to deterioration from moisture than other polymers such as polyethylene and PP. Moisture infiltration and deterioration can also be accelerated by the existence of voids, fractures, and other faults in the composite [121].

3.1.5 | High Temperature

Composite sleepers deal with a number of issues related to high temperatures. Finding materials that can endure temperatures between 537.78°C and 1093.33°C is a significant difficulty [127]. Finding lightweight materials that can replace conventional materials such as Inconel, steel, and titanium within this temperature range is still a challenge, despite the fact that composite materials have been successful in decreasing weight and optimizing design in a variety of applications [1]. Elevated temperatures typically reduce material stiffness, potentially leading to excessive track deformation [108]. Considering composite sleepers have limited strength, stiffness, and dynamic qualities and are sometimes incompatible with traditional materials, their acceptance and implementation in rail tracks have been limited [9]. To overcome these obstacles and enhance composite sleepers' overall performance in hot conditions, more research and development will be needed.

Composite sleepers are engineered to tolerate high temperatures without significant loss of structural integrity. The performance of a composite floor system under high temperatures is assessed by analyzing the slip response of angle shear connectors [104].

The shear-bearing capability of the composite floor system at elevated temperatures is found to be critically influenced by temperature and slip response [128]. An investigation into the test load behaviors of full-scale “FFU” sleepers under various support circumstances is the goal of a study [129]. The goal of the project is to create a new ISO standard for polymeric composite sleepers, which includes transoms, bearers, and sleepers. This will enhance the understanding of how the test specification requirements for the ISO standard are benchmarked. To increase its impact resistance, toughness, strength, and weather resistance, a layer of compact polyurethane composite film is applied to the composite structure sleeper, which has high strength and resistance to weather [105]. This technology produces a sleeper that is significantly strong and has the ability to absorb vibration during train operation, which reduces noise pollution and vibration while also increasing the train’s operational stability.

Hu et al. [130] highlighted that the inadequate knowledge of basalt FRP (BFRP) composites’ thermal performance at high temperatures is one of the difficulties facing the usage of composite sleepers in high temperatures. Furthermore, it has been demonstrated that ultra-highly stable CFRPs are susceptible to electrostatic discharge and environmental instabilities, which restrict their ability to be as lightweight as possible. When high temperatures are applied during manufacturing, moisture sorption in high-performance fiber-reinforced thermoplastic matrix composites (TPCs) held in ambient conditions can cause flaws and impair mechanical qualities [97]. A high filler concentration is needed to provide high thermal conductivity in polymeric composites for thermal management requirements, which complicates the polymer processing process [10]. Finally, delamination and oxidative degradation at high temperatures continue to be difficulties for ultra-high temperature ceramic composites based on carbon fiber preforms soaked with hafnium diboride, despite their promising performance [130].

According to the findings of Ferdous et al. [105], high ambient temperatures are frequently applied to railway components, particularly during the summer season. A polymeric sleeper can exhibit two distinct mechanical behaviors at temperatures below and above its glass transition temperature (T_g) [40]. When treated to temperatures much below its T_g , a polymeric material has a high modulus and acts like a glassy material; however, when subjected to temperatures over its T_g , its modulus decreases substantially, and it behaves like a rubbery material. Moisture can also alter the T_g of a polymeric composite, causing it to become low when water is absorbed [131]. However, because temperature differences can cause considerable dimensional changes in a plastic sleeper, the performance of composite sleepers at different temperatures must be examined in future research.

4 | Modern Railway Technologies in West Africa: Economic Impact, Sample Case Studies, and Challenges

West African nations are now investing in ambitious rail corridors and modern infrastructure to spur economic growth. For instance, the African Union’s Agenda 2063 envisions a pan-African high-speed rail network. The Economic Community of West African States (ECOWAS) is planning a 2,228-km rail line

linking Abidjan–Ouagadougou–Niamey–Cotonou–Lome (UEOMA) as part of the New Partnership for Africa’s Development (NEPAD) and Program for Infrastructure Development in Africa (PIDA) project [132]. New standard-gauge lines are also under development, including the Nigeria–Niger Kano–Maradi link (951 km), which will be West Africa’s first cross-border rail connection in over 70 years and is expected to significantly slash transit times and costs between Nigeria and Niger [133]. In Guinea, the €70bn Trans Guinea Railway is being built to carry iron ore from Simandou to the coast while linking interior agricultural zones and ports. Meanwhile, work on Ghana’s network north into Burkina Faso, connecting the landlocked Sahel to Ghana’s Tema and Takoradi ports, aims to coordinate with neighboring networks and unlock trade. For example, Burkina Faso’s plans have lower transport costs and multimodal trade. For Nigeria, the existing network and its planned upgrades are projected to dramatically reduce transportation costs and transit times, thereby opening new avenues for trade, investment, and regional integration. This visual integration is exemplified in Figure 8, which maps the existing and proposed railway networks in West Africa, with a focus on Ghana, highlighting key corridors, infrastructure gaps, and interconnections that underscore the regional potential for enhanced trade and mobility [134].

Such projects illustrate how rail connectivity can lower transport costs and unlock trade. For instance, the Kano–Maradi line will integrate with Nigeria’s existing network and is earmarked to dramatically reduce transportation costs and transit times, opening new avenues for trade, commerce, and regional integration. This is vital for farmers and SMEs: they can reach larger markets for cocoa, cashews, grains, etc., increasing incomes and reducing spoilage [133]. By facilitating cross-border flow, modern railways can foster a shared economic space. Rail lines bring coastal ports closer to inland producers, strengthening West African industry [133]. Plasser and Theurer [134] highlight that over the long term, this backbone of a new era of economic development will help West Africa become a more integrated, prosperous region.

4.1 | Sample Case of Ghana’s Rail Revitalization and Regional Links

Ghana’s case exemplifies the region’s shift toward modern rail. The 2013 Ghana Railway Master Plan proposes a six-phase build-out of 4000 km of new standard-gauge lines, replacing the old colonial network [134]. In support of this vision, the government created a dedicated Ministry of Railways Development. Notably, new lines are designed to extend from the Tema and Takoradi ports north to Kumasi and beyond, reaching the Burkina Faso border. This will finally link landlocked Burkina Faso to Ghana’s Atlantic ports by rail. To speed construction, Ghana has partnered with experienced contractors (e.g., Afcons, India), which also prioritizes local capacity (1150 of 1400 employees on the project are Ghanaians [134]).

These upgrades are strategically vital. Higher-speed, heavier-axle rail (designed up to 160 km/h and 25 t axle loads) will shift long-haul freight from roads to rails. This is expected to improve domestic connectivity (e.g., linking Kumasi and Northern regions) and stimulate industry in inland cities. Ghana’s project also underscores the role of public–private partnerships:

FIGURE 8 | Railway networks in West Africa/Ghana, highlighting infrastructure gaps. Note: lines shown as “In Service” represent operational segments, while “Discontinued” and “Diamond” indicate abandoned or planned extensions critical for regional integration [135].

leveraging foreign investment and technology while creating local jobs. As Ghana connects its own network and reaches into Burkina Faso, policymakers can similarly learn from these models across the region.

4.2 | Use of Composite Sleeper Technology in Africa and Sustainability

A key element of modern rail infrastructure is the railway sleeper. Traditionally made of timber, concrete, or steel, sleepers are crucial for track stability. Recent research highlights composite sleepers (made of recycled plastics, fiberglass, rubber and other materials) as a promising sustainable alternative [93]. Composite sleepers offer higher strength-to-weight ratios, durability, and environmental benefits. For example, glass fiber-reinforced polycarbonate/polyethylene sleepers exceed timber in load-bearing and durability [136]. They are also recyclable or even biodegradable, easing end-of-life disposal. Economically, these sleepers can be cheaper to manufacture and install (using waste plastic streams) than concrete or exotic hardwood, reducing lifecycle costs.

Importantly for West Africa’s sustainability goals, composite sleepers can dramatically cut carbon footprint. One study found that replacing concrete sleepers (with very high embodied CO₂) with recycled plastic sleepers can reduce overall greenhouse emissions by significant margins. Since road transport is a major source of emissions, shifting heavy freight to rail and using low-carbon rail components align with climate goals [137].

4.3 | The Need for Policy and Strategic Planning

Governments and planners should encourage these innovations. Using composite sleepers instead of wood (which contributes to deforestation) supports circular economy principles [138]. West Africa’s policymakers could adopt standards and incentives (e.g., tax breaks and public procurement) favoring sustainable rail materials, much like Ghana’s recent EU-backed timber pact to curb illegal logging in 2008. Similarly, regional strategies should

include technical standards for new materials. Funding for pilot projects (perhaps via African infrastructure funds or climate-finance mechanisms) can prove composite sleepers’ viability on African soils and climates.

5 | Policy and Implementation Strategies for Sustainable Rail

To realize these rail-led gains, coordinated policy action is needed. Key recommendations from the literature include the following:

- **Mobilize financing and investment:** As seen in UEMOA, mobilizing funds for large corridors is critical. Public-private partnerships (such as Ghana’s Afcons deal) can leverage capital and expertise. Governments and regional bodies (ECOWAS and AfDB) should establish dedicated infrastructure funds and risk-sharing mechanisms to finance cross-border rail.
- **Harmonize standards and operations:** Differing track gauges and systems impede interoperability. West African nations should standardize gauges (moving to 1,435 mm as Ghana is doing) and adopt uniform signaling/communication standards. UEMOA’s planned study on harmonizing operating systems is a step toward seamless cross-border train movement.
- **Capacity building and training:** Adoption of new technologies requires skilled personnel. Survey research in Nigeria highlights that the lack of technical know-how, training, and resources is the top barrier to railway modernization. Thus, governments should invest in training engineers and crews on advanced track-laying, maintenance machines, and digital Railway 4.0 systems. Collaboration with universities and industry (e.g., vocational programs in rail technology) is essential [139].
- **Integrated transport planning:** Railways thrive when linked to ports, hubs, and other modes. Policies should support inland dry ports and logistics centers along rail lines and coordinate rail with road, river, and air networks. For instance, the Kano-Maradi rail project complements Nigeria’s plans for inland ports, ensuring goods move efficiently to maritime gateways.
- **Sustainability and climate alignment:** Policymakers must ensure rail projects follow environmental best practices. This includes using sustainable materials (recycled sleepers and eco-friendly ballast) and energy-efficient trains. It also means minimizing deforestation for track construction; Ghana’s recent focus on sustainable forestry shows how policy can protect ecosystems. Aligning projects with the United Nations’ COP28’s rail-as-climate-solution initiatives can unlock green financing [140].

6 | Challenges and Research Gaps

Despite the promise, substantial challenges and knowledge gaps remain. Infrastructure and institutional barriers still hinder rail development in West Africa. Many existing networks are in poor condition; hence, upgrading them requires vast investment. Different national regulations and state-owned operators

complicate regional projects, requiring careful legal and commercial frameworks (as noted by rail project financiers). Even when funds are available, delays in construction can occur without stable policies and clear regulations for project management and tariffs.

On the technology front, composite sleepers face specific hurdles. While laboratory and European trials show promise, there is limited field data in African contexts. Recycled plastic sleepers may be vulnerable to UV radiation and creep over time, which are factors that could be worsened by West Africa's intense sun and variable load conditions. More research is needed on their long-term durability, thermal expansion, and cost-benefit under local soil and climate. For example, global studies call for improving plastic sleeper formulations and testing their mechanical properties in diverse environments. African rail researchers could fill this gap by pilot-installing composite sleepers on experimental track segments and monitoring performance, an area scarcely covered in the literature.

Other research gaps include:

- **Lifecycle analysis for African conditions:** While one study shows recycled sleepers cut greenhouse gases (GHGs) compared to concrete, region-specific LCA (considering local energy mixes and maintenance regimes) is lacking.
- **Economic feasibility studies:** The economics of composites (versus timber/concrete) in West Africa, accounting for material costs, transport, and maintenance infrastructure, needs a detailed cost-benefit analysis.
- **Institutional and social factors:** As Nigeria's Railway 4.0 survey found, nontechnical factors (resistance to change and unclear benefits) can slow adoption. Thus, qualitative research on stakeholder perceptions, regulatory frameworks, and capacity gaps in West African rail agencies is a priority.

In summary, implementing modern rail, especially innovative technologies such as composite sleepers, requires both engineering know-how and supportive systems. The literature points out challenges (financing, standards, skills, and technology maturity), but most studies so far are general or from other regions. There is a clear opportunity for West African scholars to investigate how composite materials perform in tropical settings, how to adapt supply chains, and which policy models work best locally. Addressing these gaps will help ensure that new railway projects in Ghana and its neighbors are not only built, but built sustainably, reliably, and for maximum socioeconomic benefit.

7 | Sustainability and LCA of Composite Sleepers

The sustainability and LCA of composite sleepers is a critical area of study, given the increasing demand for environmentally friendly and cost-effective railway infrastructure [141]. Composite sleepers, particularly those made from short-fiber plastic composites, offer significant environmental advantages over traditional materials such as timber and concrete [142]. These advantages are primarily due to their recyclability and potential for cost reduction through economies of scale and carbon pricing. The LCA of composite sleepers provides a comprehensive evaluation of their environmental impact throughout their lifecycle, from raw material extraction to end-of-life disposal. This analysis is crucial for making informed decisions about their suitability and sustainability in railway applications [77].

7.1 | Sustainability and LCA of Railway Sleepers: Global and West African Perspectives

Railway sleepers have traditionally been made of hardwood timber, concrete, or steel, each with different environmental and performance trade-offs. Recent studies increasingly examine composite sleepers (e.g., wood-plastic rot, insect attack, and bad weather better than wood), potentially reducing maintenance and replacement frequency [141]. Notwithstanding, composites face challenges too: plastic-based sleepers can creep or deform under load and may be UV-sensitive [93]. Jabu et al. [93] emphasize that timber fails by decay (termites and fungi), while concrete may crack under dynamic loads.

Global LCA studies compare sleepers on GHG emissions, energy use, and end-of-life impacts. Typical findings are mixed and sensitive to assumptions. In one LCA of a 60-year service life, Luomala et al. [5] found that concrete sleepers yield the lowest direct emissions, largely due to concrete carbonation, whereas wood (softwood) sleepers emitted more initially, but burned/incinerated wood led to the lowest total emissions over life [5]. Crucially, when reuse and recycling were considered, recycled plastic sleepers achieved the greatest GHG savings: after a second life (reuse/recycling), they had the lowest net emissions of all types. Thus, compostable plastics offer substantial benefits if recycled, as recycled plastic sleepers emerged as the material with the lowest GHG emissions over multiple cycles. Similarly, Thompson et al. [11] report that short-fiber plastic composites have clear environmental advantages once recycling is included. They find that concrete sleepers are initially cheapest, but with only 50% recycling of composite sleepers, their cost quickly matches that of concrete, especially when carbon pricing or economies of scale are considered.

Across studies, concrete sleepers often incur much higher embodied CO₂ than wood. Thompson et al. [11] note that producing a prestressed concrete sleeper can emit "10 to 200 times more CO₂" than a treated hardwood sleeper. Thus, although concrete is widely used for its strength and uniformity, its carbon footprint is large. By contrast, recycled plastic sleepers can dramatically cut emissions if they displace concrete and are recycled at the end of life. As depicted in Figure 9, the LCA of composite sleepers underscores their sustainability advantages, such as lower carbon footprints and enhanced recyclability compared to traditional materials.

The chart above in Figure 9 the carbon footprint of various railway sleepers. Although steel and concrete are resource-intensive, recycled composites show the slowest carbon footprint. The green highlight indicates the environmental advantages of diverting waste polymer into railway infrastructure, based on sustainability metrics from Tan et al. [138] and Gulcimen et al. [77].

7.2 | West African Context: Materials and Sustainability

In West Africa, railway networks historically relied on timber sleepers sourced from local hardwoods and imported materials. For example, Ghana's rail renovation in the 1980s–90s substituted locally abundant lesser-used timber species for failing imported steel and concrete sleepers, aiming to conserve scarce foreign exchange. However, years after using them, most of these

FIGURE 9 | Life-cycle assessment (CO₂ emissions) diagram for railway sleepers.

types of timber sleepers become infested with insects and are subjected to fungal attacks. This illustrates that durability issues are acute in the tropical climate. Indeed, African hardwoods such as Ekki or Azobe (used in West Africa) are considerably durable, but most of these are not termite-proof without heavy treatment.

Today, several West African countries are shifting toward concrete sleepers. Ghana recently established local concrete sleeper plants (thus an Atlantic Concrete plant in 2018) to avoid importing sleepers, reportedly saving millions of dollars annually. Concrete plants have the capacity for hundreds of sleepers per day to support rail expansion. Concrete's advantage is uniform quality and long life in service. However, no peer-reviewed LCA exists that measures Ghana's new concrete sleepers' footprint or compares it to timber or composite options in the region.

There is essentially no published LCA research on composite sleepers in West Africa. In summary, West African research is scarce: there is a lack of LCA studies of existing tracks (ballasted by wood or concrete) or comparative assessments of proposed composite alternatives in the local context.

8 | Conclusion

Composite sleepers have emerged as a viable alternative to timber, concrete, and steel, offering clear advantages in durability, recyclability, and long-term sustainability. Significant

advancements in material compositions, such as fiber-reinforced plastics, hybrid composites, and recycled polymer blends, have been highlighted by international research since 2018. These advancements resolve previous concerns regarding mechanical performance and lifespan costs. Although composite sleepers frequently have higher initial prices, life-cycle assessments typically indicate that they are more cost-effective and environmentally friendly over time because of their longer service lives, reduced maintenance needs, and recycling potential.

Despite these global advances, the adoption of composite sleepers in West Africa remains limited. The region's railway systems continue to rely heavily on timber and concrete sleepers, both of which present significant challenges: timber is vulnerable to tropical degradation, while concrete incurs high embodied carbon and infrastructure costs. Notably, no peer-reviewed studies currently evaluate the long-term performance of composite sleepers under West Africa's climatic and operational conditions. This lack of region-specific research creates uncertainty for engineers and policymakers, thereby slowing the uptake of sustainable alternatives.

Bridging this gap requires coordinated action. First, pilot studies and field trials of composite sleepers should be prioritized across major West African rail corridors to establish performance benchmarks under local conditions. Second, governments and regional bodies such as ECOWAS and UEMOA must develop technical standards, funding frameworks, and policy incentives that encourage the use of sustainable rail materials. Finally, integrating composite sleeper adoption into broader rail modernization strategies will not only reduce maintenance and environmental costs but also advance regional connectivity and economic growth by linking ports, inland markets, and neighboring economies.

This review provides a foundation for such efforts. By synthesizing global advances, highlighting sustainability debates, and identifying regional research gaps, it sets the stage for future studies and policy reforms that can enable West Africa to leapfrog toward a resilient, low-carbon railway infrastructure.

Author Contributions

Ekow Quansah: conceptualization, methodology, investigation, data curation, writing—original draft, writing—review and editing, and visualization.

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